

ULTRA-EFFICIENT WIRELESS POWERED MICRO-ROBOTIC
JOINT FOR HEALTH APPLICATIONS (UWIPOM2)*

MedtecLIVE, THE event for the production of medical technology, (2020), 30th June – 2nd July, 2020, Nürnberg (on-line), Germany, coordinator participates as visitor. [LINK](#)

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